

THE KEY TO SUCCESSFUL, SUSTAINABLE INNOVATION IS PEOPLE (?) WHAT ARE WE BETTER AT THAN AI?

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Abstract

Artificial intelligence is now a common topic in everyday conversations. Virtually everyone has an opinion about it, everyone has heard statements: AI will solve everything, AI will take our jobs, AI will solve century-old mathematical problems in seconds, AI hallucinates, AI lies. The news talks about the Nobel Prize related to artificial intelligence, the solution of the zero-day vulnerability, the successful application of artificial intelligence in healthcare, educational failures, and solving captcha and wishing the user dead.

The article's authors believe that humans are still the engine of innovation, and that AI cannot independently perform complex problem-solving tasks, complete projects, or manage change.

By analysing the innovation process and innovation ecosystem, the authors conclude that artificial intelligence can be a useful partner at almost every stage of the innovation journey. The combined use of human and artificial intelligence capacity can save time and effort, thus leading to a more appropriate or effective solution to a given problem, unmet need, or challenge.

Key words

Innovation, unmet need, co-creation, artificial intelligence

1 Introduction

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Beyond the areas of use of AI, a series of studies and books now deal with the main idea of this paper, the relationship between AI and humans in the innovation ecosystem, and raise fundamental questions such as the ethical and social impact of AI, (Pieter Verdegem, 2021) whether humans are indispensable (Borner, 2024), or what the brave new world will be like with the cooperation or confrontation of the two entities. (Szertics, 2024) The ideas

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expressed in the various studies do not paint a very optimistic picture, and according to several opinions, AI could lead to harmful discrimination (Borgesius, 2018), social inequality (Stiglitz, 2017), or even the extinction of humanity (Bostrom, 2014).

Meanwhile, researchers cannot agree on the current accepted definition of AI, let alone the interpretation of AI used in everyday speech by ordinary people. As early as 2014, Bostrom distinguished between strong or general artificial intelligence (capabilities similar to human thinking) and weak or narrow artificial intelligence (task-specific, capabilities exceeding the speed of human thinking, but not capable of independent action, only to support humans) (Bostrom, 2014). A plausible approach would be to refer to AI as a computer program that learns from and adapts to data. In his book, Elliott defines AI as “any computational system that can sense relevant context and respond intelligently to data” to efficiently perform highly complex tasks and achieve specific goals, thereby mimicking intelligent human behavior. (Elliott, 2018)

2 The current state of the problem

The development of AI is so turbulent that it is almost impossible to form a picture of the situation. The authors bravely capture a snapshot by reviewing the currently available information. This immediately raises the first real question: Is all information about the development and progress of AI publicly available? The answer is no. Do we know who the main drivers of development are? Will we notice if the big breakthrough happens? What change will the imminent appearance of quantum computers bring to this race in everyday life?

However, before we review these challenging questions, it is worth stopping at the gates of the AI world and examining whether humans are prepared for this change? It can be said that in practice, even the digital transition has not been fully implemented. We often encounter completely analog processes, or digitalization was implemented incorrectly so that analog processes were transferred one-to-one to the digital world (the paper-based form was changed to a digital form identical in all elements, so we did not achieve any quality improvement). Information previously challenging to obtain is more readily available digitally, but the completeness, quality, and reality content are increasingly challenging to verify. Another severe obstacle to the fulfillment of the digital world is that the level of digital literacy varies hugely by generation, as well as social and geographical differences. This gap is further widened by an even lower understanding of AI and recognition of its actual value, strongly questioning society's readiness to handle the next great technological leap.

1. Figure - Development stages

Source – author, own editing

If we look at the question from the perspective of what AI is currently used for and what it is not, we will not get much closer to uncovering the problem. Most of the currently known areas of AI were already known a few years ago. They belonged to the world of big data statistical calculations, which has been continuously developing with the increasing availability of computing capacities and later supercomputers. More and more sensational research and practical AI results can be heard about breakthroughs in science and practical fields that mainly require the analysis of large data sets and many repetitive activities (physics, healthcare, cybersecurity, mathematics). However, at the same time, there are more and more problems caused by hallucinations or wrong answers (lies?) from various AI models. Often, even the simplest logical tasks or anatomically accurate representation of a human hand fail in applications based on large language models.

This study will then attempt to answer what AI can be good for and what it certainly is not (for now).

2.1 Purpose of the study

This study examines the role of AI in innovation. We seek answers to which elements of the complex problems and creative thinking needs that arise during the innovation process can AI support human capacity and whether AI can complete the entire innovation cycle.

Based on the information reviewed so far, the authors argue that

- People are still the engine of innovation
- AI cannot independently recognize problems
- AI is not capable of autonomous creative problem solving
- AI is not capable of defining needs independently
- AI is not capable of managing project tasks
- AI is incapable of change management
- AI is not capable of assessing and tracking the needs and motivations of stakeholders

3 Methods used

The authors used the following methods to examine the validity of the above statements:

- Analysis of the innovation process and ecosystem
- Analysis of innovation capabilities and skills
- Stakeholder analysis

3.1 Elements of the innovation process

Many people have defined the innovation process in different ways in the past. In this study, the authors expanded the Design Thinking process (Christoph Meinel, Hasso Plattner, Larry Leifer, 2010), which originated at Stanford University, with additional elements essential for successful innovation.

The problem statement → need → idea → prototyping → testing cycle in itself usually results in a satisfactory solution that answers the problem, however, if the If solution → supporters → implementation → sustainable operation elements are not made an integral part of the process, then the solution's daily implementation and long-term successful operation are not guaranteed.

2. Figure - - Innovation process

Source – author, own editing

We will examine this expanded innovation process, looking for which elements AI can take over, complement, and support.

3.2 Human vs. AI? Complexity and required skills

The innovation cycle presented in the previous chapter mainly focuses on validating ideas and developing the resulting solution. We often do not spend enough time and energy on precisely defining the problem/unmet need and understanding the problem's target group, so the recommended solution often does not satisfy the original need. To avoid this mistake, it is worth following the steps of the mature innovation methodologies (e.g. Design Thinking), and thus, ideation and brainstorming are done with the knowledge of the precisely defined problem and target group, significantly reducing the chance of formulating the wrong solution proposal.

However, a result that reflects a real problem and offers a realistic solution is not enough to succeed. Several additional criteria must be met to achieve a new solution that is useful and functional in the long term.

The following subsection will discuss two critical elements of the process (project approach and change management).

However, even the best-organized and monitored innovation effort can fail if two additional factors are not considered.

On the one hand, without stakeholder involvement, achieving our goals will probably be much more difficult. It is important to note that although we have precisely defined our target group, we do not operate in a vacuum in the innovation space. In the world around us and that determines our activities, there will always be groups in our wider and narrower organization whose decisions, attitudes, sympathies affect our innovation efforts. Identifying the interests of these groups/individuals and, where necessary, taking them into account and incorporating them into the proposed solution can significantly boost our work's effectiveness.

The other success factor is keeping sustainability in mind. Sustainability in this context does not mean environmental impact; it examines the solution's scalability. In many cases, solutions that work well on the design board or in laboratory conditions are unusable in real life. Therefore, in addition to validating and testing the idea and solution, it is necessary to consider and examine during the introduction what challenges the implementation of the elements of the given solution into the necessary - often utterly different scale (target group size, geographical, cultural, regulatory environment) - practical environment may entail.

The spread of digitalization, further complicated by the hype surrounding the use of AI, raises an additional question regarding the skills required to implement innovation successfully.

In the analog world, sufficient depth and complexity of knowledge of the given field and the intention to change were sufficient to implement innovation.

In contrast, in a digital world decorated with AI elements, we must simultaneously be able to

- manage the digital achievements of the given field
- apply innovative methods and think creatively
- apply all the above, implement it, and lead the change

Today, practically no industry or service area does not require digitalization, whether within the narrow field of expertise, in maintaining contact with external partners, or in meeting legal requirements.

Another necessary skill is knowledge of innovation methodologies that can be interpreted in the digital world, and the willingness to apply these methodologies, and notice the problems and challenges that arise around us.

The third skill set is the ability to think project-based and operate project-oriented, as discussed in the next subsection, and the problem-oriented operation of change management.

It is already evident at this point that the complexity of the innovation process and the need to combine different skills for implementation reach a level where, at the present moment and at the current level of development of AI solutions, human added value is indispensable, AI is unable to perform tasks of such complexity and creativity on its own. However, at the same time, we should also note that this level of complexity often exceeds the level of human knowledge. In many industries, employees and managers lack basic digital skills, not to mention up-to-date knowledge of the field's digital achievements. An additional difficulty on the human side is that project-oriented thinking is often unavailable within organizations, so efforts are often wasted without supportive leadership and committed project managers and teams. Finally, as a fundamental human trait, most people experience change as a danger and a bad thing, so change management should not only involve monitoring and measuring the direction and

results of the process, but also often involves educating those involved in the process, highlighting the benefits of new solutions for them.

3.3 Change management and project approach

As discussed in the previous section, applying change and project management methodologies is key to successful innovation efforts. The purpose of this paper is not to describe the application of traditional project management tools and change management methodologies, but rather to recognize the connection that these two important success factors must become an integral part of the innovation process in today's digital world dotted with AI elements.

3. Figure - Innovation process with project and change management

Source – author, own editing

As Figure 3 clearly illustrates, the project management approach should appear immediately at the point in the process when the solution is mature enough for practical application. The key element of introducing a new product/service/procedure/process is that it is implemented in a planned, trackable, and measurable manner. The wide range of project management tools ensures that the expected time/cost/quality ratio is met and the resources spent on the project are measurable.

Unlike the introduction of project management mid the innovation process, the change management approach and methodology must be integrated into the activities from the very beginning of the innovation process. The identified problem/unmet need point of the innovation process will be the starting point of the change management, and the new solution introduced after the innovation process is completed will be the expected end point of the change management. Change management is necessary in order to be able to evaluate and measure at every point of the innovation process, whether the events are moving towards achieving the set goal, or in the event of a deviation, whether the deviation is necessary/acceptable/or needs to be corrected. This methodology also allows the participants in the innovation process to consider whether the new goal arising due to the deviation is acceptable in the event of a deviation. In this case, this goal is defined as the goal to be achieved in the future.

We must also note that AI's existence, application, and dangers have a powerful impact on the behavior of the actors in the organization and their attitudes towards change. Due to the heightened expectations associated with it, the spread of AI use is much faster than the introduction of digitalization achievements to date. Strangely enough, the aversion to digitalization manifests itself differently in the case of AI. Although we generally continue to fear the unknown, the impact, and the dangers of AI on our lives, many people believe that they can gain benefits that far outweigh the dangers of uncontrollable operations by using AI with much less effort. This duality then results in extremely positive (AI will solve everything, will cure cancer, make our lives easier) and highly damaging (AI hallucinates, lies, takes away our jobs, will end our world) news appearing in the press.

At this time, it is difficult to estimate what impact AI will have on organizations' attitudes towards change. However, it is already clear that organizations using AI can gain certain benefits. The following subsection explores this issue.

4 Co-creation potential

To explore possible collaboration, we need to examine AI's potential role in innovation processes, whether AI can independently perform the given subtask jointly with humans, and whether it is impossible to involve AI.

4. Figure - AI supported innovation process

Source – author, own editing

The supplemented diagram of the previous innovation process (figure 4) clearly shows that, contrary to previous expectations, we can use AI support in all process elements. However, let us note that all of the possible cooperation elements revealed are limited to activities previously defined as weak AI. Faster, more efficient, more extensive preliminary sorting, analysis, intermediate validation, or ex post verification of previous or newly generated data discovered during the innovation process truly creates added value compared to a process based only on human activity. Recognizing this fact, it is worth examining the possibilities and methods of human-AI cooperation in more depth.

5 Motivations and interests

The willingness to cooperate and succeed are challenging to capture and facilitate. In most cases, good cooperation and results can be achieved when the motivation and interest of the actors are aligned. When examining the role of stakeholders in the traditional innovation process, we need to approach the issue from several angles. Whose problem is the identified problem, and what is the target group's problem? Does the given problem also affect other actors, and to what extent? Is there anyone outside the target group who can do something to solve the problem, and does he have the power to do so? Can we do something to involve and motivate these actors? What factors drive the parties involved in the problem – power interests, personal relationships, financial interests, social interests, or are they only involved based on personal persuasion?

When we combine AI's role into this complex problem and stakeholder map, we can quickly see two things. The previously mentioned difference between the acceptance of digitalization and AI implementation significantly changes the interests of the original actors, as the general belief is strong that the use of AI represents a power and/or economic advantage compared to the traditional approach. Therefore, in exchange for the perceived (or real) advantage, those involved are willing to accept or forgo the increased risks (e.g., a significant increase in cyber exposure).

The other effect, however, is even more significant. Redefining the entire conceptual system becomes necessary if we include AI as a stakeholder in innovation. We need to determine AI's motivation since AI does not have material, power, social, or self-realization goals and interests that correspond to our current range of interpretation.

6 Decision factors

Another factor to be examined is the decision as a matter of human, managerial, and organizational need. According to the norms accepted today, decisions must be made continuously during the process to utilize innovation results. Depending on the subject and location of the innovation, this decision may be made at the level of the given person or a smaller group. However, the decision is usually made within some organizational framework, along with hierarchical relationships, considering the rules and laws applicable to this given organization. Many factors influence the decision, but the organization's interest, the (even if different) interests of the given person or group, our personal experiences, impressions, and our willingness to take risks certainly play a role. Making a decision is further coloured by whether there is individual or group responsibility, whether we think along operational or strategic goals, and finally, whether we keep short-term or long-term effects in mind.

In the previous chapter, we saw that AI does not have goals or interests in the traditional sense, meaning it cannot base its decisions on these criteria. AI will factor in the pre-programmed rules and criteria and finetune the decision based on the complexity and size of the dataset on which the AI was trained. So, can AI make accurate decisions? Can it take responsibility for its decisions? Can it consider the moral and ethical circumstances of its decisions? Not in the original human sense, and realizing this, we must agree that complex and sensitive decisions (for example, healthcare diagnoses) must be supervised and validated by human actors.

7 The main findings of the article

By analyzing multiple perspectives, one thing can be stated for sure: AI is already part of our everyday lives in many areas, and given the speed of development and progress, this will

most likely remain so. Considering the development stages presented earlier, the digital transition that has not yet occurred will most likely turn into an AI transition, with all its advantages and dangers. The pressure on market and social actors is also clearly outlined, and there is a strong feeling that whoever is left out will be left behind.

Although AI is not yet capable of achieving sustainable, effective innovation results on its own, there are activities that can be automated, well parameterized, and algorithmized at practically all points of the innovation process. The added value of AI through faster and more accurate data analysis is unquestionable, which ultimately leads (or at least might lead) to better, more effective innovation results.

8 Conclusion

The study previously stated that the field is developing and changing so rapidly that it is almost impossible to form a comprehensive picture of it, and an assessment that seems realistic today may lose its meaning tomorrow with the publication of another development milestone. One thing is sure, the development of AI requires continuous monitoring, and without claiming to be exhaustive, here are some challenging questions to conclude:

- Are we aware of the dangers and risks of using AI?
- Can current regulations keep the development of AI within limits?
- Do we understand how the resilience of companies and organizations is changing with the increasing use of AI (cybersecurity, data protection, ethics, control, power)?

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